

FOUNDATIONS FOR CREATING SAFE AND HEALTHY WORKING CONDITIONS IN THE MANUFACTURING SECTOR

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Abstract: The results of scientific research on existing problems and their elimination in order to create safe and healthy working conditions in the production sector are presented. The article also contains a scientific proposal formulated by the author and practical recommendations on this issue.

Key words and phrases: labor protection, certification, safety techniques, dangerous and harmful factors, accidents, production, "Human-Machine-Environment" system, safety, guidance.

Research Relevance: Labor is an inseparable part of our lives, and we all desire not only fair wages but also safe and comfortable working conditions. Numerous legal, organizational, and technical efforts are being undertaken by our country's President and Government in this area. Labor legislation is progressing in line with our country's economic and social development. For instance, the adoption of the new editions of the Labor Code, the Law on Labor Protection, and various other laws and regulations can be cited. Although compliance with labor laws, workplace injuries, occupational diseases, and accidents in production have decreased in industrial enterprises, there is still much progress to be made. Thus, this topic remains **relevant** today and necessitates scientific research.

According to data from the International Labour Organization (ILO), every year, 2 million people worldwide (over six thousand each day) die due to workplace

accidents and occupational diseases. Additionally, these figures are increasing by 10% annually. Furthermore, 270 million people become victims of workplace incidents. In CIS countries, more than 600,000 accidents are reported annually. According to the ILO, 4% of the global Gross Domestic Product is lost due to unsafe working conditions and accidents at work.

Research Objective: The research aims to ensure labor safety in industrial enterprises, protect the health of employees, and establish healthy and free working conditions.

Based on the research objective, the following **tasks** will be addressed:

1. Examining and analyzing normative, legal, and technical documents in the field of labor protection and safety engineering.
2. Studying issues related to labor protection and safety engineering in industrial enterprises and developing recommendations.

Main Body: Humanity's long historical experience confirms that any activity carries potential risks. This understanding is widespread, although in production environments, it is possible to manage and reduce the level of risk. However, achieving absolute safety is impossible in any situation.

For this reason, research on ensuring safety in human labor activity dates back to the works of Aristotle (384–322 BC), Hippocrates (460–377 BC), as well as Russian scientists M. V. Lomonosov, D. L. Kirpichev, and medieval scholars like Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, and Ibn Sina (Avicenna), among many other notable figures.

From the early years of its independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has aligned its political, social, and economic directions with international standards, guided by the principle of the state as the primary reformer. This alignment is consistent with the documents of international organizations. The United Nations (UN) adopted the “Universal Declaration of Human Rights” on December 10, 1948. Article 9 states, “Everyone has the right to life...,” and Article 23 adds, “Everyone

has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favorable conditions...”icle 42 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is stated: “Everyone shall have the right to work, to free choice of profession and activity, to working conditions that meet safety and hygiene requirements, to fair remuneration without any discrimination, not less than the established minimum wage, and to protection from unemployment in accordance with the procedure prescribed by law” . This pligns with the aforementioned Declaration and confirms Uzbekistan's commitment to these international principles.

Every year on April 28, World Day for Safety and Health at Work is widely celebrated globally. This day highlights the significant efforts of the International Labour Organization (ILO). Under the ILO’s initiative, events in Uzbekistan are organized with themes such as “My Life, My Job, My Safe Work” to raise awareness of labor protection and safety issues.

Today, the concept of occupational safety and health is one of the most pressing and serious issues on a global scale. The international standards for labor protection include the following requirements:

- Protecting the health and life of workers;
- Establishing national standards for labor protection and ratifying international documents;
- State management of labor protection;
- Conducting government oversight to ensure compliance with labor protection requirements;
- Facilitating public oversight regarding the implementation of labor protection requirements;
- Coordinating labor protection efforts with the preservation of environmental cleanliness and other types of social and economic activities;
- Financing labor protection projects at the state level;
- Supplying qualified specialists in labor protection;

-Creating a unified information system for labor protection, among other measures.

According to the norms adopted in the ILO's 52nd Convention, the International Labour Bureau (ILB) developed the "Guidelines on Occupational Safety and Health," which specify methods for proper risk assessment and identification, as well as a system for managing risks. This legal document provides recommendations on correctly assessing risks in the workplace, managing them at national and regional levels, eliminating hazards promptly, and developing a system for safe working conditions. This ultimately fosters growth in the social, economic, and technical fields.

In line with these efforts, numerous international standards that align with our country's legal framework have been ratified by our Parliament's Legislative Chamber. The government's initiatives in labor protection are positively recognized by international organizations. A clear example is the ILO meeting held in Tashkent in 2021 and the Asian Forum on Human Rights held in Samarkand in November 2023.

At the same time, the work being done in the field of occupational safety across all sectors of the economy cannot be considered fully positive. In particular, today in many construction processes, the safety of workers' lives cannot be fully ensured. We have often witnessed builders working 20–30 meters high on unstable platforms in extremely hazardous conditions. While skyscrapers are of great importance, it should also be noted that no building construction is worth risking a human life.

In our country, safety regulations have been established for all types of activities, including specific technical standards, norms, and rules for builders. Unfortunately, these requirements are not always fully implemented, which should be a serious concern for construction organizations. As a result, the number of accidents among workers continues to increase.

Furthermore, primary workers are often hired on a temporary basis, and studies have shown that, firstly, employers do not formalize employment contracts with them. Secondly, due to the large size and heavy weight of construction materials like cement, shingles, wood, and wood products, private entrepreneurs are compelled to hire additional unofficial workers to load, transport, unload, package, guard, and sell these goods, as a single hired worker cannot handle these tasks within the legal limits. This issue is not limited to the construction sector but is even more problematic in small contracting firms and in the agriculture sector. Consequently, unofficially hired workers lack occupational safety and protection, leading to accidents that are neither investigated, analyzed, nor formally documented.

This lack of documentation prevents injured workers from obtaining future social protection in accordance with regulations, hinders the recording of their work history, and affects their ability to receive fair pension payments in the future. This situation leads to an increase in disputes and violations of occupational safety requirements.

According to existing technical documentation, loading and unloading tasks are classified as heavy and hazardous work, with the weight that a worker can lift during a single task limited to 15 kilograms, and the total weight lifted over the course of a work shift not exceeding 870 kilograms. However, the weights of items such as cement, potatoes, carrots (each bag weighing 50 kg), shingles, and wood products exceed these standards. Therefore, it is impractical to fully comply with these limits in practice.

Comprehensive reforms implemented across the Republic have been creating a significant number of job opportunities each year. Efforts are underway to align occupational safety measures with international standards, but unfortunately, this is still insufficient. It is observed that due to disregard for occupational safety requirements and failure to provide workers with safe working conditions in various

economic sectors, the number of work-related accidents is increasing.

Creating safe and healthy working conditions in economic sectors, particularly in construction organizations and agricultural job sites, remains a pressing issue, as there are still numerous factors that pose risks to workers' health and lives. The demand for certification of these jobs and improving workers' qualifications based on their roles continues to grow.

The certification of work environments based on working conditions is a comprehensive measure aimed at assessing the compliance of labor conditions, the intensity and heaviness of the work process, and the risk of injury with regulatory and technical requirements in the field of occupational safety. This process involves identifying harmful and hazardous production factors to ensure a safer work environment.

Certifying workplaces offers several benefits for workers, particularly for those in heavy, uncomfortable, hazardous, or harmful jobs. The main purpose of such certification is to establish benefits and compensations for employees as stipulated by law, assess occupational risks, ensure that workers are provided with personal and collective protective equipment, and facilitate the early diagnosis of occupational diseases. Additionally, certification is mandatory for workplaces employing individuals with disabilities, all jobs at hazardous production facilities, and specific occupations.

Employers also benefit from this certification process. If workplaces are not certified and the safety requirements are neglected, employees working in these conditions have the right to demand various compensations or refuse to work, especially if their health and lives are at risk. This could reduce the economic efficiency and productivity of the organization and potentially impact the economy of other enterprises as well. Without certification, it cannot be guaranteed that working conditions are safe.

According to Article 14 of the Occupational Safety Law, organizations with

certified workplaces see reduced legal disputes, fewer occupational illnesses and injuries, and optimized spending on compensation payments, which could eventually be reflected in the cost of manufactured products.

When signing contract agreements, parties are mutually responsible for implementing safety measures in designated work areas. Organizations are also required to train newly hired employees on safe working methods as specified in employment orders. Article 25 of the Occupational Safety Law mandates this training to ensure compliance with safety standards.

The state's labor protection policy has various directions, each focused on ensuring the dignity of human life and prioritizing the health and safety of workers. In our rapidly developing country, issues such as reducing energy consumption, increasing productivity, and improving working conditions are central priorities.

Despite the introduction of mechanized and automated robots in production and the improvement of control systems through specialized computer programs, human factors remain a constant issue awaiting resolution. This is because every technological process is ultimately controlled by humans, making accidents and incidents in production inevitable. Human psychology is such that, occasionally, production-related errors occur.

In the field of labor protection, the Ministry of Employment and Poverty Reduction is the specially authorized state body responsible for developing and implementing state programs, coordinating the labor protection activities of state and economic management bodies, and setting labor protection requirements for all organizations. It monitors compliance with labor protection standards and inspects these requirements, provides social protection for workers who suffer accidents or occupational diseases, combats forced labor, ensures gender equality, and oversees poverty reduction efforts.

One might ask if these initiatives are being effectively implemented. Indeed, these achievements required significant effort, especially in protecting the labor

rights of minors and eliminating forced labor. Many years of control over compulsory labor and the employment of minors have strengthened, and scientific and practical work continues to create safe and healthy working conditions. Seminars on labor protection have been organized at the district, regional, and national levels.

It is necessary to conduct informational sessions for the leaders of state and private non-governmental organizations about the principles and laws related to labor protection, especially regarding the protection of workers' rights in cases of forced labor and unhealthy or heavy work conditions. Discussions should be held with these leaders to encourage them to create suitable job positions.

As our country progresses beyond the stage of forced labor, it is now essential to educate employers on providing decent working conditions for every citizen who starts employment. Currently, seminars are being organized with the participation of company and state organization leaders to provide these necessary explanations.

Despite the various reasons behind workplace accidents, a significant cause lies in some employers prioritizing profit in a market economy, often neglecting a healthy work environment and ignoring safety standards for employees.

Therefore, organizations are facing challenges in properly implementing labor protection measures, creating safe and healthy working conditions for employees, and preventing accidents. There is also a lack of systematic oversight of ongoing work and insufficient enforcement of legal mechanisms for ensuring accountability among those responsible. Additionally, the absence of legal mechanisms for integrating project safety requirements into the construction and production processes further complicates accountability.

Conclusion: In recent years, extensive reforms have been implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure the safety, health, and preservation of workers' lives and work capacity during labor processes. Specifically, four main authorities in the field of labor protection have been realized:

- the transfer of labor protection services to professional market participants;
- strengthening of state and public control over labor protection;
- improvement of working conditions in enterprises and organizations, focusing primarily on workplace environments;
- prevention of injuries in production.

Nevertheless, we continue to witness numerous workplace accidents, often due to employer incompetence, lack of knowledge among workers, or other contributing factors. Each of us must identify and promptly address these shortcomings without leaving the responsibility solely on one individual. This means that everyone should feel accountable for their own safety and health.

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